

VHTR Benchmark Calculations of the Coarse Mesh Coupled Neutron-Photon Transport Method

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ABSTRACT

The continuous-energy coarse mesh transport (COMET) method/code was recently extended to include coupled neutron-photon transport for obtaining the power (energy deposition) distribution in heterogeneous reactor cores. In this work, the new (i.e., extended) COMET is benchmarked against the continuous energy Monte Carlo code MCNP in a very-high-temperature reactor (VHTR) single-block full-length configuration with and without reserve shutdown channel. In both cases all heterogeneities including TRISO fuel and burnable absorber particles, the helium gas coolant, and the graphite moderator/reflectors are explicitly modeled. It is found that the solutions obtained by the two codes are in excellent agreement. The eigenvalue differences are 73 pcm and 91 pcm with a combined uncertainty of 13 pcm for the problems without and with the reserve shutdown channel, respectively. The average difference in the pin-cell power distribution is 0.26% and 0.35%, with the combined uncertainty ranging from 0.15% to 0.35% and 0.16% to 0.37%, respectively. Additionally, COMET is found to be about four orders of magnitude faster than MCNP, demonstrating that COMET achieves continuous-energy Monte Carlo-level accuracy while providing exceptional computational efficiency (i.e., about 2 minutes on a single compute core). This capability makes COMET particularly well-suited for solving coupled neutron-photon transport problems with multiple levels of heterogeneity, such as those encountered in VHTR analyses.

Keywords: Coupled neutron-photon transport, numerical radiation transport methods, reactor analysis, power distribution

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate prediction of the power (energy deposition) distribution resulting from coupled neutron-photon transport in a nuclear reactor is essential for reactor analysis, design, and optimization. The continuous energy coarse mesh transport (COMET) method [1-3] was recently extended and implemented to solve coupled neutron-photon problems in heterogeneous nuclear reactors [4]. The resulting new COMET [4] consists of the following two solvers: (1) a local continuous energy stochastic transport method to solve a set of local fixed-source coupled neutron-photon transport problems to generate response functions for each unique coarse meshes such as fuel lattices/blocks, reflector/moderator blocks, and (2) a deterministic global sweeping solver to converge the outgoing neutron and photon partial flux moments crossing coarse mesh interfaces via the pre-computed response function library prepared in step 1. The new COMET method was benchmarked in a single PWR assembly with and without control rods have demonstrated the high accuracy and computational efficiency of COMET [4]. In this work, we further benchmark COMET against MCNP [5] in a full-length single-block very-high-temperature reactor (VHTR) with and without reserve shutdown channel [6]. These problems are challenging to any deterministic methods because of their neutronics characteristics such as multiple heterogeneities resulting from the TRISO fuel and burnable absorber particles, the helium gas coolant, and the graphite moderator/reflector.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The coupled neutron-photon COMET method [4] is briefly presented in section 2. The numerical benchmark calculations against the continuous Monte Carlo

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reference results are discussed in section 3. Concluding remarks and future work are found in section 4.

2. COUPLED NEUTRON-PHOTON COMET METHOD

The energy deposition distribution in a nuclear reactor can be obtained by solving the following coupled neutron-photon transport equations.

$$\mathbf{H}_N \psi_N(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \frac{1}{k} \mathbf{F} \psi_N(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) + \mathbf{Y}_{PN} \psi_P(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) \text{ for } \vec{r} \in V, \quad (1a)$$

$$\psi_N(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \mathbf{B} \psi_N(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E) \text{ for } \vec{r}_s \in \partial V \text{ \& } \hat{\Omega} \cdot \hat{n} < 0, \quad (1b)$$

and

$$\mathbf{H}_P \psi_P(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \mathbf{Y}_{NP} \psi_N(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) \text{ for } \vec{r} \in V, \quad (2a)$$

$$\psi_P(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \mathbf{B} \psi_P(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E) \text{ for } \vec{r}_s \in \partial V \text{ \& } \hat{\Omega} \cdot \hat{n} < 0. \quad (2b)$$

In the above equations, V denotes the spatial domain of the problem, \hat{n} denotes the outward norm at the external boundary ∂V , ψ_N and ψ_P represent the neutron and photon flux at spatial position \vec{r} , direction $\hat{\Omega}$, and energy E , respectively, \mathbf{H}_N and \mathbf{H}_P are the standard neutron and photon transport operators, \mathbf{F} stands for the fission operator, \mathbf{B} denotes the homogeneous (vacuum or specular) boundary operator, \mathbf{Y}_{PN} is the photonuclear operator, and \mathbf{Y}_{NP} stands for the neutron-induced photon operator which includes fission gamma, inelastic gamma, and (n, gamma) reactions. [4]

The coupled neutron-photon method starts with subdividing the spatial domain V into a number of non-overlapping regions $\{V_i, i = 1, \dots, N\}$ such as fuel assemblies and reflector/moderator blocks. These regions are referred to as coarse meshes in COMET. It is assumed that the outgoing/incoming neutron and photon fluxes can be expanded in terms of a set of orthogonal expansion functions as below:

$$\psi_{\alpha, is}^{\pm}(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \sum_m J_{\alpha, is}^{\pm, m} \phi_{asy}^{\alpha}(E) \Gamma_m(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E) \text{ for } \vec{r}_s \in \partial V_{is}, \alpha = N, P, \quad (3)$$

where $\psi_{\alpha, is}^{\pm}$ represent the outgoing (“+”) or incoming (“-”) neutron ($\alpha = N$) or photon ($\alpha = P$) flux on ∂V_{is} , $J_{\alpha, is}^{\pm, m}$ are the expansion coefficients (phase space moments) on ∂V_{is} , $\phi_{asy}^{\alpha}(E)$ is the asymptotic spectrum [4], and Γ_m are the expansion functions that meet the orthogonality relation. By using the orthogonality of the expansion functions, the outgoing/incoming expansion coefficients can be calculated as:

$$J_{\alpha, is}^{\pm, m} = \int dE \int_{\partial V_{is}} d\vec{r}_s \int_{\hat{\Omega} \cdot \hat{n}_{is}^{\pm} > 0} d\hat{\Omega} (\hat{\Omega} \cdot \hat{n}_{is}^{\pm}) \psi_{\alpha, is}^{\pm}(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E) \Gamma_m(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E). \quad (4)$$

Based on the incident flux response expansion theory [2], the neutron and photon flux in any coarse mesh can be computed as a superposition of the contributions responding to each incoming flux moment imposed on the coarse mesh boundaries:

$$\psi_{N, i}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \sum_{\alpha, s, m} J_{\alpha, is}^{-, m} \mathcal{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) \text{ for } \vec{r} \in V_i, \quad (5)$$

and

$$\psi_{P, i}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \sum_{\alpha, s, m} J_{\alpha, is}^{-, m} \mathbb{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) \text{ for } \vec{r} \in V_i. \quad (6)$$

In Eqs. (5) and (6), $\psi_{N,i}$ and $\psi_{P,i}$ are the neutron and photon flux in coarse mesh i , $\mathcal{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E)$ and $\mathbb{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E)$ are the neutron and photon surface-to-volume response functions, respectively. They can be obtained by solving the following two local fixed-source coupled neutron-photon transport equations:

$$\mathbf{H}_N \mathcal{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \frac{1}{k} \mathbf{F} \mathcal{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) + \mathbf{Y}_{PN} \psi_P(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) \text{ for } \vec{r} \in V_i, \quad (7a)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \begin{cases} \phi_{AS}^N(E) \Gamma^M(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E), & \text{for } \alpha = N, \vec{r}_s \in \partial V_{is} \text{ \& } \hat{\Omega} \cdot \hat{n} < 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7b)$$

and

$$H_P \mathbb{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \mathbf{Y}_{np} \mathcal{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}, \hat{\Omega}, E(w_i)) \text{ for } \vec{r} \in V_i, \quad (8a)$$

$$\mathbb{R}_{is}^{\alpha M}(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E) = \begin{cases} \phi_{AS}^P(E) \Gamma^M(\vec{r}_s, \hat{\Omega}, E), & \text{for } \alpha = P, \vec{r}_s \in \partial V_{is} \text{ \& } \hat{\Omega} \cdot \hat{n} < 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8b)$$

Projecting Eqs. (5) and (6) onto the expansion basis, one can calculate the outgoing neutron/photon partial current moments as:

$$J_{\alpha, is}^{+,m} = \sum_{\alpha', s', m'} R_{i\alpha' \alpha s' s}^{m' m}(k) J_{\alpha', is'}^{-,m}, \quad (9)$$

where $R_{i\alpha' \alpha s' s}^{m' m}$ are the surface-to-surface response coefficients which are precomputed and stored in the response library by projecting the surface-to-volume response functions onto the expansion basis.

It can be seen from Eqs. (8) and (9) that surface-to-volume and surface-to-surface response functions depend only on the geometry configuration and material compositions of the coarse meshes. It is noted that those local fixed-source problems are defined in the coarse meshes which are small in mean free paths and have vacuum boundary conditions. As a result, a continuous energy stochastic solver is very suitable for precomputing/generating the response functions. Once the response function library is generated, a deterministic sweeping solver consisting of the following two nested iterations is used to compute the global solution (the eigenvalue and power distribution).

- Inner iterations: Eq. (9) is used to repeatedly update outgoing neutron and photon currents until they are converged.
- Outer iterations: The global balance equation is used to calculate the core eigenvalue, and the fission neutron generation separation method [7] is used to update the response coefficients until the global solution is converged.

Ultimately, the energy deposition distribution in a coarse mesh can be computed as a superposition:

$$ED_i^j = \sum_{\alpha, s, m} RE_{ias}^{jm} J_{\alpha', is'}^{-,m}, \quad (10)$$

where ED_i^j stands for the energy deposition in region j of coarse mesh i , denoted as V_i^j , and RE_{ias}^{jm} represents the response energy deposition coefficients which can be tallied during the response function generation.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Both the eigenvalue and power distribution computed by the COMET code are compared to the direct continuous energy Monte Carlo reference solutions in the benchmark problems [6]. The ENDF/B-VII.0 library is used by both COMET and MCNP.

3.1. VHTR Single-Block Benchmark Problems

VHTR is a Generation IV reactor concept characterized by a graphite-moderated, helium-cooled thermal core. Accurately modeling this reactor presents significant challenges for neutronic simulators due to its complicated geometry, and multiple heterogeneities from TRISO fuel particles embedded within the fuel pins and burnable absorber particles dispersed within the poison pins. The full-length single fuel block [6] consists of a two-layer bottom reflector, a ten-layer active fuel zone, and a two-layer bottom reflector. The height of each layer is 79.3 cm. Specular boundary condition was assumed on the six radial external surfaces, while vacuum boundary condition was imposed on both the top and bottom surfaces. The following two configurations were considered in this work:

- Case 1: a single-block problem without reserve shutdown channel
- Case 2: a single-block problem with reserve shutdown channel.

Figure 1. VHTR Component Blocks (from [6]): Fuel Block (top left), Fuel Block with Reserve Shutdown Channel (top right), Reflector Block (bottom left), Reflector Block with Control Channel (bottom right).

A detailed radial view of the fuel and reflector blocks is shown in Figure 1. In this figure, gray indicates the graphite structure, yellow represents fuel pin regions, green corresponds to burnable absorber pins, and white denotes channels for the helium coolant. The total number of fuel pins, burnable absorber pins, and helium coolant pins are given in Table I, and their geometrical specifications are summarized in Table II.

Table I. Total number of pins.

Assembly	Fuel Block with Reserve Shutdown Channel	Fuel Block with Reserve Shutdown Channel
<i>Fuel Pin</i>	210	186
<i>Burnable Absorber Pin</i>	6	6
<i>Helium Coolant Channel</i>	108	95
<i>Reserve Shutdown Channel</i>	N/A	1

Table II. Geometry Specifications.

Assembly pitch	36 cm
Pin cell pitch	1.8796 cm
Fuel pin hole radius	0.635 cm
Absorber pin hole	0.635 cm
Large coolant channel radius	0.794 cm
Small coolant channel radius	0.635 cm
Reserve shutdown channel diameter	4.7625 cm
Number of axial layers	14
Number of layers in active zone	10
Height of each axial layer	76.3 cm

The multiple heterogeneities of the problem arise from the fact that the fuel and burnable absorber pins contain millions of explicitly modeled Uranium Oxycarbide TRISO fuel particles and burnable poison particles. The TRISO fuel particles are modelled as cubic lattice with a side length of 0.09664222 cm in both MCNP and COMET. The geometrical specifications of fuel and burnable poison particles and material compositions can be found in Ref. [6].

3.2. Benchmark Calculations

The MCNP reference calculations were performed on a 96-core cluster. Ten million particle histories are first run to converge the fission source distribution, and then 5 million inactive and 25 million (1,250 active cycles with 20,000 histories in each cycle) active particle histories are used to perform the actual calculations for each core configuration. Despite the fact that the single-block benchmark problems are small in the radial direction, it is still extremely time-consuming to tally the detailed energy deposition in the entire problem. As a result, the energy deposition distribution in each pin-cell is tallied only in the 6th and 10th axial layers (from the bottom).

For the COMET calculations, the four unique coarse meshes as shown in Figure. 1 are used to model the single-block benchmark problems. The stochastic continuous energy response function generator (modified MCNP) is then used to pre-compute the response coefficients for all the unique coarse meshes. The expansion orders (4, 4, 2 and 2) are used on the two spatial and two angular variables, respectively. The neutron and photon energy distributions are expanded by the product of the asymptotic spectra [4] and the 0th order B-splines. The response function library is precomputed with 10 million particle histories in each calculation. The total pre-computation time is 21 hours on a 64-core cluster. The response function library is then used to perform COMET core calculations for the two benchmarks. It is noted that the response function library generation is a one-time investment, similar to the industry practice of generating the cross section library for core calculations. Once those response functions are compiled into a library, it can be used for an arbitrary core configuration composed of those coarse mesh/lattice types.

The core eigenvalues calculated by COMET and MCNP and the corresponding computation times are presented in Table III.

Table III. Comparison of the core eigenvalues and computation times.

Problem	MCNP*	COMET**
	Eigenvalue	1.09326 ± 0.00008
Case 1	Difference (pcm)	73
	Run time (hr)	40.08
	Eigenvalue	1.08385 ± 0.00009
Case 2	Difference (pcm)	91
	Run time (hr)	35.26
	Eigenvalue	1.08294±0.00011

* MCNP calculations are on a 96-core cluster with the detailed energy deposition distribution tallied only on the two axial layers. It is estimated that it would take about 10 days if the detailed energy deposition distribution were tallied on each axial layer of the entire problem.

**COMET calculations are performed on a single core of the cluster with the detailed energy deposition distribution calculated in the entire problem (i.e., all axial layers).

It can be seen from Table III that the eigenvalues predicted by COMET and MCNP are in good agreement. That is, the differences are 73 and 91 pcm for the two single-block VHTR problems, respectively. The COMET full-block calculations take only about 2 minutes on a single compute core, while the MCNP calculation on a 96-core cluster for the two configurations take about 40 hours and 35 hours with the energy deposition distribution tallied only on the two selected axial layers.

Figure 2. The axial energy deposition distribution computed by COMET for the single-block VHTR benchmark problem without reserve shutdown channel

Figure 3. The axial energy deposition distribution computed by COMET for the single-block VHTR benchmark problem with reserve shutdown channel

The COMET energy deposition distributions are plotted in Figures 2 and 3 for the two configurations, respectively. The comparison of the energy deposition distributions (power) computed by COMET and MCNP is summarized in Table IV using the following four statistical parameters:

- AVE: the average relative difference
- MRE: the energy deposition weighted relative difference.
- RMS: the root mean square of the relative differences
- MAX: the maximum relative difference.

Table IV. Comparison of the energy deposition distribution computed by COMET and MCNP.

Problem	Fuel Block	Fuel Block with Reserve Shutdown Channel
AVG	0.26%	0.35%
MRE	0.19%	0.21%
RMS	0.36%	0.41%
MAX	1.04%	0.96%

It can be seen from Table IV that the energy deposition distribution computed by COMET and MCNP are in excellent agreement. The average relative differences are 0.26% and 0.35 for the single block without and with reserve shutdown channels, and the maximum relative differences are 1.04% and 0.96, respectively. It is noted that MCNP uncertainties vary from 0.15% to 0.37%, while the COMET uncertainties change from 0.04% to 0.07%. As a result, the discrepancies between the codes are within the three standard deviations of the corresponding uncertainty. We note that the COMET uncertainties are underestimated because the correlations among the fuel pins are ignored. Otherwise, the COMET uncertainties should be comparable those of MCNP. Including the correlations are future work.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The coarse mesh coupled neutron-photon transport code COMET is benchmarked against the continuous energy Monte Carlo reference solutions for two single-block full-length VHTR problems. It is found that both the eigenvalue and energy deposition distribution predicted by COMET agree very well with the corresponding reference results obtained by the continuous energy MCNP. The eigenvalue differences between the two codes are 79 and 91 pcm for the two benchmark problems, respectively. The average relative differences in the energy deposition distributions are 0.26% and 0.35%, which are within three standard deviations of the Monte Carlo uncertainty. It is also found that COMET is about four orders of magnitude faster than direct Monte Carlo calculations, despite the fact that the energy deposition distribution is tallied only in the two selected axial layers in Monte Carlo. While COMET computes the energy deposition distribution in every axial layer in the problems. This indicates that new COMET can solve coupled neutron-transport problems with accuracy close to that of continuous energy Monte Carlo while maintaining a formidable computational speed.

As future work, COMET benchmark calculations will be extended to full-core problems.

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DISCLOSURE

The second author owns equity in a company that has licensed the COMET technologies from Georgia Tech. This study, which is a demonstration of COMET, could affect his personal financial status. The terms of this arrangement have been reviewed and approved by Georgia Tech in accordance with its conflict-of-interest policies.

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